

THE IMPACT OF THE INFORMATIZATION PROCESS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract: in this article, one of the pressing problems of today is thinking about such issues as the behavior of people in the information society and the formation of skills to be able to properly use information in this process.

Keywords: Information, Society, Development, media, cyberspace, electron commerce, market.

ВЛИЯНИЕ ПРОЦЕССА ИНФОРМАТИЗАЦИИ НА РАЗВИТИЕ ОБЩЕСТВА

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Аннотация: в данной статье одной из актуальных проблем современности является осмысление таких вопросов, как поведение людей в информационном обществе и формирование навыков умения правильно использовать информацию в этом процессе.

Ключевые слова: Информация, Общество, Развитие, СМИ, киберпространство, электронная коммерция, рынок.

INTRODUCTION

The process of informatization has become an integral part of modern society. Today, the development of Information Technology and communications, the possibility of quick and easy access to information, as well as the transformation of social ties and economic activity have a huge impact on the development of society.

In this article, we will consider the impact of the informatization process on the development of society.

The process of informatization allows people and organizations to quickly and easily access information. Through the Internet and digital technologies, anyone can find the information they need in a matter of seconds.”It is natural that the informatization of society introduces social changes to the lifestyle, communication and relationships of the population. Information circulating in the media can also be harmful, as well as corresponding to the material and spiritual interests of the state, society and the individual. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, new types of cyberspace crimes affect the social vision and goals of young people and also generate new social information values.

MAIN PART

Social networks provide us with sites where we can communicate without offense with family and friends. In this case, cybercriminals will continue to commit theft of personal data of people in social networks. Not only in social networks, but also in bank agreements, all security” focused on ensuring.”¹This, in turn, creates favorable conditions for the exchange of knowledge and experience. People will have the opportunity to improve their knowledge, learn new skills and become aware of the news in their field. Information technology helps to make the educational process more efficient and interactive.

Through online courses, webinars and other educational resources, many people acquire new knowledge and skills. Distance learning opportunities extend educational opportunities, especially for students living in remote areas. This process helps to improve the quality of education and meet the demand for education.

The process of informatization enhances communication between people through social networks and other means of communication. People will have the opportunity to express their opinions, discuss problems and help each other. This, in turn, increases mutual understanding and cooperation in society. Through social media, people have the opportunity to communicate their thoughts to a wide audience. Information technology helps to make economic activities more efficient. Businesses are able to process information quickly and make decisions. Through digital marketing, e-commerce and other innovative solutions, companies will be able to bring their products to a wide audience.

This process leads to economic growth and creates new jobs. The process of informatization plays an important role in the dissemination and development of culture and art. Art, music and other cultural heritage can be reached to a wide audience via the Internet. This, in turn, promotes cultural exchange and increases mutual understanding between different cultures. The process of informatization helps to involve citizens in political processes. People have the opportunity to express their opinions, discuss problems, and actively participate in political decision-making. This process strengthens democratic processes and develops civil society. Information technology encourages innovation.

In the process of developing new ideas and technologies, information exchange is important. Innovation, on the other hand, promotes economic growth and Community Progress. In general, the process of informatization accelerates the development of society and leads to positive changes in its various areas. Factors such as access to information, education and training, social interaction, economic development, culture and the arts, political participation and innovation show the impact of the informatization process on the development of society. Therefore, the development and effective use of the information process is important for the future of society. The information being disseminated through the information process may not always be reliable and accurate.

Yalan information, rumors, and manipulated information can distract people and cause them to make wrong decisions. The process of informatization can also negatively affect privacy. Problems such as the spread of personal information on the internet, cyber attacks and interference in privacy can occur. This reduces people's sense of security. Manipulation of information for

¹ Rakhmatov D., Akhatov A. Cybercrime occurrence factors and cyber ethics: problems and solutions// Science and Education Journal. 2021. –No. 1 (1). 227 (. www.openscience.uz)

political and economic interests can lead to people changing their minds and exacerbating social problems.

This, in turn, reduces trust in society. The informational process, along with many positive effects, also has negative effects. To reduce these negative effects, it is important to control the quality of Information, protect personal information and promote social interaction. It is necessary for people to be conscious in order to use information wisely and avoid its negative effects. In general, the process of informatization accelerates the development of society and leads to positive changes in its various areas. In today's digital age, the Society of Information Exchange plays a pivotal role in shaping communication, knowledge dissemination, and collaboration among individuals and organizations. This society is characterized by its emphasis on sharing information through various channels, including technology, social media, and traditional communication methods.

The primary goal of the Society of Information Exchange is to facilitate the flow of information, which is crucial for decision-making, innovation, and progress. In a world inundated with data, the ability to filter and disseminate relevant information is more important than ever. Effective information exchange not only enhances personal and professional development but also fosters collaboration across different sectors. Technological advancements have revolutionized the way we exchange information. The internet, social media platforms, and mobile applications enable instantaneous communication, breaking down geographical barriers. Online forums, webinars, and digital publications allow experts and novices alike to share insights, experiences, and knowledge, promoting a culture of learning and growth. Despite its many benefits, the Society of Information Exchange faces several challenges.

CONCLUSION

The overwhelming volume of information can lead to misinformation and confusion. Additionally, not all information is created equal; the credibility and reliability of sources must be critically evaluated. Ensuring that information is accessible to all, including marginalized groups, remains a significant hurdle. The Society of Information Exchange is essential for fostering a connected and informed global community. As we continue to navigate the complexities of the digital landscape, it is imperative to prioritize effective communication and collaboration. By addressing the challenges associated with information sharing, we can build a more informed and equitable society.

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